

>> “The ripe time to attack”

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If I were the Aliens...

Let's just assume they are real and could even be reading this!

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Re: Use of Strategy & Shi to determine the ripe time to attack, from the aliens' perspective

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

To Whom It May Concern;

In the consideration of the New Cold War, which is comprised of (a) the Cultural Civil War, (b) the World War 3.0, and (c) the asymmetric attacks of the West's strategic enemies, chiefly China and Russia, or other anti-NATO and pseudo-NATO allies who play the horizontal-vertical game of "entangled alliances" 'by ear' (aka "fair weather friends"), the author has the following proposal.

- ❖ The most opportune time for the supposed/alleged aliens to attack (or for a fake alien attack/false flag to be planned) is approaching, perhaps by the year 2025-2027

Why do I say this? Consider the dropping values of the Innate Shi of the United States¹, and likely worse the NATO allies, which are getting less allied². Consider the likelihood that the covert space program has been compromised either by China or during transition from the US Department of the Air Force to the US Department of the Space Force, in the May 2021 transition.

Consider the high likelihood that China, Russia, and others know of or are even replicated the "vimana"³ type devices built by Space Command⁴, which were secretly led by covert Majestic-12 operatives and other similar organizations⁵, for over 40 years.⁶ Most of the computer systems appear to have been compromised. The advantage that they are enjoying in IQ assets is increasing, and China's advantage there - while budget has not and may never catch up - will not diminish even when their population wave is cut in half. Most of the IQ assets or potentials in the form of immigrant-offspring will not come online for 10-20 years before entering service. Furthermore their average IQ is a good 10+ points below China's⁷ and that means TIQ may lag 15-20 points or more as our education system continues to fail to evolve. What we are talking about is a very real ability to solve complex engineering problems - as quickly as possible.

A number of new technologies are also going to have subtle to overt effects upon the Innate Shi (via technology as a 0th soft domain⁸ spread throughout all domains of war.)

1

https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1

2 https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

3 <https://airpowerasia.com/2020/08/27/vimana-the-ancient-indian-aerospace-craft-time-for-indigenisation/>

4 <https://krdo.com/news/2020/08/31/space-force-or-space-command-whats-the-difference/>

5 <https://www.cs.mcgill.ca/~abatko/interests/conspiracy/mj12/>

6 <https://www.amazon.com/Space-Force-Future-Secret-Programs-ebook/dp/B0916GD4KV>

7

https://www.academia.edu/50652106/China_vs_the_World_IQ_as_a_Strategic_Asset_a_graphical_comparison

8 MIMS 2.8 is definitely affected by MIMS 2.2, and a great treatise is had on this in SPR 2.0 Pt1 and https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System pp. 42-68, and pp. 142-148

- Artificial Intelligence
- Deep Fakes
- Procedural generation
- Virtual Reality
- Next level drone
- Cyborgs
- Androids and robotics
- LiDAR and new level bathymetry
- Directed energy weapons and WMD
- Quantum computing
- Carbon infrastructure development
- Thorium nuclear
- Crypto blockchain
- Data analytics*
- Nanobots

Consider then, the 9th and 12th stratagems:

- Watch the fires burning across the river 隔岸觀火
- Take the opportunity to pilfer a goat 順手牽羊

They are perfect “chain stratagems” 連環計 for the overall “to Loot a Burning House” 趁火打劫.⁹ What benefit does this enable? Once mankind is at each other’s throats - digitally, or conventionally - in the World War 3, which China thinks it will win by making America just hand over the mantle of Ba 霸 (hegemon), and Russia thinks it will win via roll-up and reformation of a stronger USSR 2.0... that is the perfect time for an alien race to roll up the entire planet!

In most of our science fiction the aliens strike without warning. It is doubtful the aliens would risk nuclear fallout and toe to toe war with the humans which is what would happen if we were suddenly assailed (due to our present countermeasures protocols).

First they would scientifically study and build AI to understand and take over all of the domains in a complete rollup. Especially AI and computing. They might be hyperdimensional aliens or little green men, it wouldn’t matter we would still be at a technological inferiority. Even if they use digits (just as I type this with mine), they would undoubtedly have high end brain to digital transfer technology and super speed processing as well as far more advanced Operations Research (of which Data analytics is but a part).¹⁰

Therefore the main concern is that they could control any of the following:

- Laws of Physics
- Forces of Physics
- Data leylines
- Math wars
- The Power of Numbers

⁹ The name of my forthcoming Strategy Series novel

¹⁰ For our side we have far too little emphasis on Operations Research sciences, and sadly in particular, are feeling the effects of poor logistics planning irrespective of the laws (known or unknown) of nonlinear dynamics and fractal/complexity theory.

- The Aether
- Connection to our God/Lord/Source**
- The climate
- The Solar System Electric Circuit
- Gamification
- Propaganda Force-fields
- Electrostatics
- Biological Information Spheres (bacterosphere, virosphere, fungisphere, etc.)

Via these highly “unconventional” and “unorthodox”¹¹ methods, they could theoretically gain a much more superior advantage, even by studying this paper, than is presumed in “The Day the Earth Stood Still” or “War of the Worlds.” Both of these rely a bit on *deus ex machina* to solve the crisis, which I find wholly unconvincing and unreliable as a defense mechanism in a real War of the Worlds.^{12 13}

Our main defense, of course, is the vastness of space. But now that we have violated the “Dark Forest Principle”^{14 15 16} and assuming we have not the Thicker Face or Blacker Heart^{17, 18} in such a war, what could be done?

Let’s go back to the proposed alien strategy. Something it’s already in play with ancient alien bloodlines. Of course, these people also believe everything is controlled by the “Jews”, apparently not via high IQ but some sort of *Jewish Conspiracy*.¹⁹ So what if the bloodlines are actually part alien as in a “The Arrival” meets “They Live” type scenario? Chances are good then, that the proposed Triumvirate is everywhere, and enjoying our worker bee, hive-mind, self-domesticated efficiency as a rare Universal commodity of parallel processing, to achieve rapid advancement. Chances are good they’d not be much more advanced than us, and chances are just as good that they wouldn’t want war with us, but to be us - assuming we are not the aliens we’ve been looking for (but arriving on Earth by other ie-astral means!)

Nevertheless, if the strategy is to attack by confusion, take by obfuscation, and destroy via distraction... what *could* be done in a pre-conventional and defacto conventional war?

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism

¹² * being a part of the science known as Operations Research

¹³ ** in ancient AOW (bingfa) concepts, those with Heaven’s Will survived, and those who went against Tao perished

¹⁴ “Dark forest theory” holds that civilizations fear one another so much that they don’t dare to reveal themselves lest they immediately be considered a potential threat and destroyed.”

<https://techcrunch.com/2019/01/20/technologys-dark-forest/>

¹⁵

<https://bigthink.com/surprising-science/the-dark-forest-theory-a-terrifying-explanation-of-why-we-havent-heard-from-aliens-yet/>

¹⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/Dark-Forest-Remembrance-Earths-Past/dp/0765386690>

¹⁷ https://archive.org/details/thickblacktheory_201604

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/36789475/Thick_Face_Black_Heart

¹⁹ In my experience, Jews are smart and the Universe favors intelligence and family values, whether or not they are ‘God’s Chosen People.’ Therefore we can expect the same elites to be Jewish or not Jewish, and the proposition of far right extremists (and their leftist compatriots in socialist politics) to fix the problem was both evil and a failed experiment.

The reliance upon mechanical and kinetic in the buildup is ill advised. But setting aside the control of all physics, then the best thing is *during* actual conventional war to rely upon analog and mechanical computing and weaponry, especially rail gun and other ballistics, which would almost assuredly pierce all conventional grade 1 and 2 force fields and perhaps challenge the dominance of a grade 3 force field level military (think: Independence Day).

In my opinion then, the key would be to flush out co-conspirators, whether they are overt allies, or possessed of demonic frequencies²⁰ and mind-controlled²¹, to make them separate and distinct from the fairly homogenous homo sapiens sapiens consciousness framework: however tribal, asinine, rural, backwards, racist, or untranscended. Then from this isolation, take and study them, preferring science over cold malice, and discern the overall strategy. Design AI androids and augment humans to cyborgs working with technologies, and then fight a forward war in a domain not on Earth. The key would be also to delay, delay, delay while we develop. But our development would need to be unified and removed from the knowledge of the enemy.

Now, assuming alien technological supremacy, which is the only safe assumption to make about one's enemy, we must - and this is key - dissimilate or obscure our minds and plans, and make them difficult to understand.

When the time to overtake and attack comes, we must rely on irrational modes of being, such as bloodlust, emotions, passionate battle, all controlled by a bellicose supreme commander who nevertheless would not attack Heaven's Host if it suddenly appeared to aid or to judge. If Heaven's Host is not already a part of the alien conspiracy but is a dimensional veil opening up mechanism, as is presumed by most Christians and marvel comics' purveyors, then we should be wary of accidentally shooting at the host. By all accounts any seraphim and cherubim would not play even handed with mankind if they did not have the restraint of our Lord. Assuming the Lord Himself comes "not to bring peace but a sword," we also must assume that to Him all of us are "alien" whether we are extraterrestrials, or demons with human skin, or just sinners caught up in a web of sin and evil (like sex traffick rings and gangs, mafias, etc.) As far as we could understand to the cherubim the AI androids would be the least sinful among us, but being born of our sinful natures, it seems likely to be an offense to the Creator, and considered part of Legion²². So **mankind must be careful not to be judged as part of Legion**.

In which case, let us suppose that we are able to challenge the Lord of Hosts²³, it would be a classical mistake to confused the power to oppose with the right to. Just because we can unlock the secrets of Aether, the Plasma-electromagnetic Force, multidimensions, hidden maths and occult powers, including the innards of the atom, and can fight toe to toe mechano-kinetically and ballistically with extraterrestrial cousins, humanoid or otherwise, carbon or silicon based... doesn't mean we have the right to challenge the ascended host of Heaven. To do so would probably result in annihilation of the physical existence of the planetary mass of Earth and the disintegration atomically of all of our being and collective mass, as well as erasure from the "game server" of humanity²⁴, on soul and spirit level, until it is as if we never existed.

²⁰ It isn't clear that the hyperdimensional aliens would be allies, co-children as we, or enemies of the Heavenly Hosts in Revelations. It might depend upon the form of multiverse they come from as there are at least 6 forms of multiverse to consider.

²¹ Including by the CIA or cartels - slaves of any sort

²² And he answered, saying, "My name is Legion; for we are many." Mark 5:9

²³ <https://sarata.com/bible/verses/about/hosts.1.html>

²⁴ <https://www.vox.com/future-perfect/2019/4/10/18275618/simulation-hypothesis-matrix-rizwan-virk>

As for the alleged alien subversion, it would only need to go on so long as it took to get people completely addicted to unreality: social media, instant gratification apps, virtual realities, a life of luxury and entertainment, etc. Once the people were completely cows²⁵, there'd be little to no fight/resistance left in them. When the water is full of fluoride²⁶, chlorine, drugs and hormones, and mankind completely gives up on fixing this, the chemical cocktail will weaken the genetic signal in people and lead to a population ripe for the harvesting. What that harvesting looks like is not exactly clear. There is no objective proof that there is a systematic snatch and probe program by alleged aliens, but there are lots of people who have passed mental psychiatric evaluations and yet maintain they were the victims of abductions and scientific experiments.²⁷ Curiously, though, they always return with all their working limbs and glands, sense organs etc. and there is no outer sign in most cases of anything more than burns which could have easily been self-applied. So if they were all abducted and experimented upon, what is the reason and what are the results?

The author would propose that the best purpose would be to study one's enemies' emotions and thoughts, sense reactions and behaviors. Essentially, what we do with leopards and cheetahs, bears and lions: tranquelize, tag, study, and release.

In such a case, we can look at what a lesser animal would do - if it could - about the veterinarian. Firstly, the animals outnumber and have more raw power than their vet captors. So if only they could become aware of the danger and phenomenon, then they could organize and resist.²⁸

➤ Mankind does not have to win, he only has to make conquest unpalatable.

The worst way to do this, of course, is "Scorched Earth" practices²⁹. The extreme of which was displayed in the "Second Renaissance: part 2" anime, where the humans try to defeat the AI robots by blotting out the sky.

Figure 2 - Operation Dark Storm (gif); credit: "Animatrix"/WB

²⁵

<https://www.science.org/content/article/early-humans-domesticated-themselves-new-genetic-evidence-suggests>

²⁶ <https://bebrainfit.com/fluoride-neurotoxin/>

²⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Supernatural-Meetings-Ancient-Teachers-Mankind/dp/1932857842>

²⁸ Except the aerial advantage. Therefore analogously we need electrodynamic drives and spaceships.

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scorched_earth

These kinds of next level M.A.D. ideas are pointless. A superior species or robot army would find ways around this, and new energy sources, etc. The main idea in making something unpalatable is actually not to ruin the planet or the countryside, ala the Russians trying to defeat Napoleon. Although a temporary slash and burn did work there. It is to make it confusing, weird, and when the aliens think they have conquered, to harry them with nasty unorthodox techniques. There will always be some weakness to any enemy, no matter how strong. Therefore, it is a matter of finding it:

- Taste for flesh
- Sexual strangeness
- Physical limitations
- Phobias
- Obsessions
- Pride and arrogance
- Chokepoints, shatterpoints, etc.
- Places of frequency
- Pleasure houses and riches
- Etc.

Now, as to possible superiority of might, in defense and offense, there are the possibilities mentioned in previous SPACER works, such as thunderbolt generators, plasma and magnetic shielding, and of course the proposed inertially dampened electric flyers.

Figure 3 - "Tic-tac" UFO ([gif](#)) ; credit: USAF/New York Times

Supposing that the known UFO "tic-tac" and others like it - spheres etc. - are not US Space Command (now Space Forces) aerial vehicles, run in a complex, hidden war against the aliens already... but are in fact active threats, then we have no choice but to engage these

threats in our best manner. If their agents have infiltrated not only the Pentagon but the secret black book programs, CIA or other organizations, as well as Russian, ESA, and Chinese space commands... then it will be difficult to develop without being sabotaged.

In the “Three Body Problem” it was proposed that the aliens sent along “Sophons” which were electrons made 2D and programmed then made 3D again to move at the speed of light. They were embedded with AI so as to disrupt human scientific development. Mankind could not go beyond present physics (because particle accelerators were blocked) and was forced to use

“Wall Facers” to come up with secret plans to stop the aliens.

Figure 4 - Samaritan Program in 3BP, used to track the number of escapists who could align to aliens ([gif](#)); credit: 10thandnoble³⁰

I suggest we institute exactly this program, but thousands of wall facers. Each of them should

come with a dozen or more chained strategies and report back to independently verified human - and completely loyal to humanism and no trans humanism or alien mania - leaders. These leaders should tactically convene with one another, protecting the identities of the wall facers, and no centralized database kept. These leaders can try one another out, trying to elicit notes on the basics to compare the ideas, to get a rough idea on good defenses. An independent and secret panel of people who have been proven to be superhuman, via practice Qigong, prayer, yoga, etc. and consuming strong human culture and foods, could then review these programs. They can come up with a series of public, secret, “secret” and supersecret solutions which are then put to important governments. What is leaked should be partially true and mostly lies, so as to confuse the alien enemies. Wall-facers should not be encouraged or even allowed to meet one another. They should be identifiable in an alien crisis by some secret proof and then able to get to the human defense centers to be consulted about the true implementation of their plans.

As the aliens and AI would be likely to read this, it would be advisable that the wall-facers choose their own non-flesh-and-blood successors to communicate with in a paper-only manner (which is then disposed of, and all wall-facers would need acute visual memories³¹), and never digitally or leaving any obvious trace. The aliens (or their agent-slaves more likely) should not be able to abduct the five top contacts of the wall-facers with a high likelihood of success. Nor should they be able to poison or assassinate the top 20 or even 50 with a high rate of success of eliminating successors. Over time the wall-facers could inculcate upwards of five new wall-facers a decade, to ensure the continued success. Because each

³⁰ <https://10thandnoble.wordpress.com/2017/08/21/the-dark-forest-by-cixin-liu/>

³¹ Probably using “memory palaces”

leader, wall-facer, and successors would exist as independent cells, with unique proofs, which nevertheless could be proven to be authentic by protocol, there should be no expectation of a complete elimination of the wall-facing program.

Most of them, by far, will come up with the same stupid, asinine ideas. Most of these ideas, even the best ones, will not work. Most of those ideas which could work will be logistically difficult or even impossible. But if the program expands sufficiently then we can expect the complexity (via simulations) to produce actionable resources at some point. Storing these in these specialized meetings has the added benefit of improving mankind's defenses while also delaying the leadership of aliens as they become unsure of their success. Presumably the more precise their engineering, the more careful their natures. Only when they have assumed a 99.98% chance of success are they likely to consider the time nearly right, in my opinion. Right now, if they exist, it is the nuclear and saucer programs which keep things likely from progressing.

However, nothing is known for sure, and that is the most dangerous thing. We cannot spend a trivial amount, nor a superfluous amount on this program. Probably 7% at minimum, 13% if we are serious, and that's being fairly generous. As I said there is no point in making starship battle cruisers. In the Liu Cixing trilogy the humans try this and get basically wiped out. We are not likely to have an "Ender's Game" situation fighting a horde of hive minded. I do not think that a computer virus would work, either, as in "Independence Day." So the question is, why persist in these delusions? Instead, our fleet should be formed for expansion to forward

bases, and our defense at each level should rely on a) observation posts, b) solid stone defenses, c) multiple homes, and d) ballistica/rail gun, in my opinion.

Figure 5 - Railgun penetration ([gif](#)); credit: US Navy

I'd be interested to see other SPACERS respond. I wonder how many would offer up

chemical warfare as a solution. I do not think nanobots or chemical warfare, or genetic attack, are good options, but we should expect exactly these types of attack. However, at this time it isn't clear what could be done about them.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

Figure 6 - The Sentinel (cover) swarm ([gif](#)); credit: "The Day the Earth Stood Still" (2009)

Appendix - These are apparently not aliens, but extraterrestrial angels (would we attack them?)

Figure 7 - the Heavenly Host?

Figure 8 - Cherubim; credit: Demonic Paradise Wiki³²

Figure 9 (next page) - Cherubim in Ezekiel 1; credit: Wong/Couk³³

³² <https://the-demonic-paradise.fandom.com/wiki/Cherubim>

³³

<https://tonymaritis.medium.com/ezekiel-1-vs-10-the-cherubim-has-a-face-of-an-ox-whats-the-face-of-a-cherub-92cc9bca571c>

Figures 10-12 - Seraphim?³⁴ ³⁵; seriously speaking if they can track and adopt our technology, it would be unwise to treat them as aliens in a war.

³⁴ <https://mcgshield.org/1377/fiction/a-catholic-learners-guide-to-biblical-monstrosities-1-the-seraph/>

³⁵ <https://astronlogia.com/occult/archangels/seraphim-angels/>